

Periodic and Multiperiodic Coronavirus Evolution: Phase Space Methods to Visualize Pandemic Data and Models

Joseph J. Molitoris

mhmolitor@aol.com, West Long Branch, NJ 07764

Professor of Physics and Former Fellow of the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation

(ITP, FIAS, University of Frankfurt, Frankfurt, Germany) and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN, University of Catania, Catania, Italy)

Abstract

A novel technique to analyze and visualize pandemic data and models is presented. Based on the fact that the system evolves in a loop (or two) in phase space, the path length and phase angle in the loop are relevant measures. In analogy to a complex physical system, the phase space for a pandemic consists of the variables (cases, deaths) and their derivatives or changes (new cases, new deaths). We focus on the new cases and new deaths variables. Both of these start out low (typically zero deaths and one or a few cases), rise to maximum values, and then reduce again to zero or low numbers if the pandemic wanes in the case of a periodic evolution. In the case of a second loop, the pattern repeats either with a higher or lower maximum value. The approach is illustrated for several regions of the world (e.g. Brazil, China, Germany, Pennsylvania, New York City, and New Jersey). In each case, our lognormal model is applied for reference purposes; however the computational analysis and visualization technique is model independent. Our ap-

proach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities. In the multiperiodic case, the pandemic will begin a second cycle as is seen in Pennsylvania and Louisiana. In the aperiodic case, no cycle is yet apparent: this may be the situation for the World, Brazil, and other states or countries until a loop is evident. Government officials can use these methods of analysis and visualization in real time to guide decisions about social and economic restrictions, where and when appropriate.

1. Introduction

The coronavirus outbreak has taken the world by storm leading to serious economic and social upheaval. Fortunately, the pandemic appears to be nearly complete in the far east (China, Japan, South Korea) as well as other regions (New York City, New Jersey, Germany, Spain, Italy) of the world. There is some evidence of a second bump in the curve in some cases (e.g. Pennsylvania and Louisiana), either smaller or larger than the first wave. The average citizen has been subjected to nearly daily briefings by mayors, governors, presidents, and prime ministers. We present a simple novel phase space approach and computational analysis technique to visualize and track this and other pandemics. The ideas are based on work done by the author some years ago in nuclear phase space dynamics [1] initially applied to the coronavirus pandemic in March [2].

2. Models and Simulations

Early efforts at understanding disease outbreak focus on the simple logistic model, which has two parameters S and r : a saturation population and a growth rate. The equation for this model is: $y = S/[1 + (S-1) e^{(-rt)}]$. The binomial model, which has an infection probability p , may also be used to describe disease outbreaks and evolution. These models, perhaps because of their simplicity, are limited in use and accuracy [2].

A basic time stepped simulation [1,2] can be used to better describe the data in a region. Again, there are two parameters S and r . S the “susceptibles” is the long term population that becomes

infected; r is the growth rate or transmission coefficient. The differential equation that the computer simulation solves is: $dy/dt = r y (1-y/S)$. The precision of the simulation can be verified by comparison to both exponential growth and logistic model growth, respectively. With a time step of 0.1 day in the simulation, the percent error versus the logistic equation is typically less than 0.1 %.; in all the calculations shown here 0.01 day is used.

To include death and recovery requires a bit more sophistication in the model. The single differential equation is changed to a coupled set of four equations:

$$(1) \frac{dy}{dt} = r y (1-y/S-R/S-D/S) - b y - d y$$

$$(2) \frac{dx}{dt} = -r y (1-y/S-R/S-D/S)$$

$$(3) \frac{dR}{dt} = b y$$

$$(4) \frac{dD}{dt} = d y$$

where y is the number of Infected, x is the number of Susceptibles, R is the Recovered, and D is the Deaths. Note that since $x + y + R + D = S$ a constant, the sum of the above four differential equations is zero. The parameters b , d , r , and S must be extracted from experimental data of the pandemic and can be adapted to the situation as the disease spreads. The initial conditions that permit the solution of the differential equations using a fixed time step procedure are that at $t=0$, we have $y = 1$, $R = D = 0$, and $x = S-1$. The basics of this type of modeling were developed over 100 years ago [3] and are still in use today in a variety of contexts. Though details of the models (sometimes called SIR for susceptible, infected, recovered) used by decision makers are not given in government briefings, typically this type of model is of use.

The cumulative number of cases $Y=y+R+D$ follows a similar set of four coupled equations. A function which fits the periodic coronavirus case and death data fairly well is the hyperbolic tangent: $Y = 1/2 S (1 + \tanh r(t-m))$ where r is again a growth rate and m is the mean or location variable. This is not surprising since under certain conditions the hyperbolic tangent and logistic function are equivalent and the logistic function is a first approximation.

By straightforward differentiation of the hyperbolic tangent equation and the use of the Pythagorean identity for hyperbolic sine and cosine squared, one obtains

$$(5) \frac{dY}{dt} = 2 r Y (1 - Y/S)$$

which is analogous to equation (1) above. This may be coupled with the below three equations to obtain an alternate differential equation (D.E.) model.

$$(6) \frac{dx}{dt} = -2 r Y (1 - Y/S)$$

$$(7) \frac{dR}{dt} = b y$$

$$(8) \frac{dD}{dt} = d y .$$

Since the cumulative number of cases $Y = y + R + D$, the first equation (5) of this alternate model may also be rewritten as $\frac{dy}{dt} = 2 r Y (1 - Y/S) - by - dy$ which replaces (1) and makes it clear that the condition $y + x + R + D = S$ is satisfied.

We program the simulations in Mathematica [4]. There is not in most of the cases investigated a significant difference between the phase space results of equations (1) to (4) termed “y D.E.” versus the the alternate model of (5) through (8) labeled here as “Y D.E.”.

See Figures 1 and 2 for comparison of Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and World Health Organization China (Figure 1a), NJ (Figure 1b), France (Figure 2a), and Italy (Figure 2b) data [5-8] to our time stepped simulation models. These type of simulation models are adaptive in the sense that as the pandemic spreads, the model results improve in accordance with new baseline data. The data used in this paper is as of September 2020. Since the models given here adapt as the data is rolled out in real time, what is important is the phase space visualization and computational analysis method.

3. Path Length

The path length of the loop in phase space is more of an integral measure of the pandemic progress in a region of the world. Examples of the path length are shown in Figures 6 through 9 for Pennsylvania, Michigan, Mexico and New York state respectively. Figure 11 gives the end loop path length for over 20 regions (cities, states, countries); we have also computed values for USA and the World, but these are off scale and so not shown in the figure. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

4. Phase Space

Our way of interpreting the data or model of the pandemic in a region (city, state, country) is thus via phase space [1,2]. Looking at the coupled differential equation models (equations 1 to 4 or 5

through 8), all of the quantities y , Y , D , R , x as well as their derivatives may exhibit interesting behaviour. Plots of dy/dt versus y or new cases versus new deaths give useful information [2]. These orbits in phase space (see Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4) define the scope of the pandemic and allow visualization of both disease spread as well as progress towards the desired end of the pandemic event. Unfortunately, not all of the variables may be readily available in reported statistics. The quality of the reported data [5-8] is also highly variable.

Since the total number of cases (cumulative Y) as well as the number of new cases - and the corresponding death data - are readily available, we have proposed [2] plotting new deaths versus new cases observables. Examples are shown in Figures 2 and 4 for France and Pennsylvania [5-8], respectively. The data may either be viewed as a type of random walk or as smoothed connected points. We use a smoothing interval of 5 days; the actual interval does not matter greatly and the unsmoothed data may also be plotted with the fluctuations if desired.

Either way, the phase space picture amounts to a type of random walk in a nearly contained region of phase space. The trajectory of the random walk or the smoother model data is from pandemic start (1 or a few new cases and new deaths) to finish (0 or few new cases and new deaths). In Figure 2 it is seen how France has completed the phase space orbit as the infection there wound down over the summer; rebound with a second loop is of course possible as in Pennsylvania (Figures 3, 4, and 5). Another infection outbreak can occur or the disease may rebound, but still the phase space visualization plot is useful and can show that.

This type of phase space region display thus allows for the possible near containment of the data into a phase space area where the path to mathematical extinction (pandemic end) can be better seen. The new case data, however, can be somewhat noisy due to small numbers, fluctuations, and reporting issues. Indeed, the reported data is often subject to corrections and even the late reporting or adjustment of data [5-8]. In order to improve that data for visualization purposes, a smoothing over several days may be used (again we use five days). The distributions of mathematical statistics can also aid in data visualization and understanding. Further, the new case and new death data can each be fit by a lognormal, normal, gamma, hyperbolic tangent, or other distributions (see Figures 1-5 for sample simulation results versus the data). More results are shown in Figures 6 through 18 for other regions of the world. China, Korea, and Japan have completed or nearly completed the phase space orbit and if there is a rebound, it can be seen quickly in the phase space visualization. New York City, New Jersey, France, Italy, Spain, and Germany are also found to be well on their way to completing the phase space orbit. Some evidence of post-orbit noise or rebound is found in several cases. Brazil, U.S.A. as a whole, and the World are in the middle of their phase space evolution.

5. Probability Distributions

Since the number of confirmed cases for a pandemic reaches a maximum as the disease runs its course in a region, pretty much any of the probability distributions from mathematical physics

and statistics [9] may be used to model or fit the data. It is mainly a matter of a normalization constant and shifting of the distribution by the mean. The cumulative number of cases Y equals S times the cumulative density function (c.d.f.). The rate of change dY/dt equals S times the probability density function (p.d.f.). The four coupled differential equations then are:

$$(9) \quad dY/dt = r(t) = S * \text{p.d.f.}$$

$$(10) \quad dx/dt = -r(t)$$

$$(11) \quad dR/dt = b y$$

$$(12) \quad dD/dt = d y .$$

As in equations (1) to (4) and (5) through (8), the quantity $Y+x = y+x+R+D = S$ is a constant.

These equations may be solved using a time stepped method as used above [2]. Alternatively, the statistical distribution may be fit to the data using standard methods. An equation for $R+D$ may be found when Y is an integrable function by the use of an integrating factor with the equation $d(R+D)/dt = (b+d)y = c (Y-R-D)$. In some cases, as with the lognormal distribution, the integral can be done numerically. This allows extracting other relevant variables that may not be directly measured or reported (see Figures 2b, 5, and 18).

In order to better simulate the data our standard lognormal reference model includes both Gaussian noise and primary harmonics, which are present in the data. The noise is easily seen by subtracting smoothed data from the unsmoothed data. The harmonics are seen as bumps in the power spectra of cases or deaths (see Figures 10 and 16 as examples). Sometimes the noise washes out or overshadows the harmonics so that they are not easily seen in the cases data.

For New Jersey, the correlation coefficients are .9979 (Lognormal) and .9983 (Weibull). For California the correlations are also pretty good: .9959 and .9970. Correlations for China are .9973 (Lognormal) and .9996 (TANH model). We are correlating the entire time vector of the model distribution with the cumulative cases of the data for all the days of the infection. Typically there are 150 to 250 values in that time series vector from disease outbreak (1 or 2 first cases at $t=0$) to thousands of cases at disease peak.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients for cumulative confirmed case data versus the lognormal model.

Region	Correlation
World	0.9991
U.S.A.	0.9981
China	0.9973
New York City	0.9991
United Kingdom	0.9966
Germany	0.9995
France	0.9998
Italy	0.9987
Spain	0.9994
New Jersey	0.9996
California	0.9959
South Korea	0.9947

We have examined a plethora of probability distributions seeking those that seem to work best.

The Chi-squared and non-central t distribution under and overshoot too much to be of use, but

the others work fairly well. The gamma, normal, hyperbolic tangent, Weibull and lognormal distributions are found to work the best with correlations of .9930 to .9995, depending on the region of the world. Table 1 gives lognormal model correlations with the data for the cumulative confirmed case data; similar results are found for the deaths data.

6. More Phase Space

The phase space plots (e.g. Figure 1) are suggestive of a nearly elliptical contained region in phase space. This is most easily seen in the normal and lognormal distribution models. The main axis of the ellipse defines an angle. The angle may be found by fitting a line to the data or other methods (data matrix diagonalization). The magnitude of the angle relates to the severity of the pandemic in terms of mortality per confirmed cases. This is shown in Table 2 below as well as Figure 12. Angles from the lognormal distribution reference model are also shown.

Table 2. Pandemic death flow phase space angle F compared to confirmed case mortality rates.

Note that China adjusted their death count upwards in early May; thus a range of mortality is shown. In New York City the range shown depends on whether one counts the “probable deaths” or not. The referenced model is based on the lognormal distribution and equations 9 through 12.

Region	Phase angle (data)	Phase angle (model)	Mortality rate
South Korea	0.60	1.04	0.024
U.S.A.	1.43	1.54	0.029
China	1.57	1.66	.040-0.055
Brazil	1.65	1.31	0.057
Japan	1.94	2.78	0.053
Germany	2.02	2.55	0.045
New Jersey	3.96	4.19	0.077
New York City	4.74	4.74	.084-0.109
Italy	7.92	7.77	0.141
United Kingdom	8.09	8.91	0.155
France	10.43	9.14	0.185

Our approach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

A useful “clock” phase space angle can be obtained by referring the phase space plots to the center of the phase space region. This angle P is defined with respect to the vector that goes from this center point to the origin and thus begins at small values around the death flow angle F, flips to 180 degrees at half cycle, and then flips to 360 degrees at completion. In terms of the evolution of the pandemic we can define a clock time $T = 24 (P - F) / 360$. If P, F are in degrees then T

is the clock time on a 24 hour scale from midnight to midnight. The time on the clock is shown in Table 3 for several sample regions (date again are as of July).

What time is it on the pandemic scale? As the clock time approaches midnight, the pandemic is done (unless it rebounds in another cycle). The angle locating where the pandemic is in its orbit cycle can be paired with the cumulative case numbers at that time to create a polar or radar type graph; see Figure 1b. Of course, if the disease rebounds then that also is seen readily on a radar clock plot. Some details of the pandemic evolution are also seen in a power spectrum plot of the data; see Figure 10. The power spectrum, as well as our phase space new death/new case plot are useful in understanding the nature of the periodic vs aperiodic pandemic evolution [2,10].

Table 3. Pandemic clock phase space angle P translated to clock time of the pandemic in the region. Initially the phase angle is pretty close to the death flow angle. At around noon the pandemic is producing the most new cases and new deaths. After flipping to 360 degrees, the number of new cases and new deaths has decreased and will tend to zero or a few if the pandemic ends without rebound.

Region	Date	Phase angle (data)	Phase angle (model)	Clock time
New Jersey	March 15	F=3.9	F=4.2	0:00
	April 19	184	184	12:00 noon
	May 12	358	359	23:36
Japan	January 31	F=1.9	F=2.8	0:00
	April 13	180	181	11:52 AM
	May 5	357	354	23:40
New York City	March 7	F=4.7	F=4.7	0:00
	April 14	205	188	13:12
	May 7	367	366	Just past 24:00 midnight
United Kingdom	March 24	F=8.1	F=8.9	0:00
	April 21	188	185	11:59
	May 26	362	368	23:35

The two steps that a typical pandemic (such as the recent coronavirus one) passes through can be seen in Table 3 and all the figures. On the first step (near noon on the clock scale), the phase angle is near 180 degrees or pi radians. At around noon the pandemic is producing the most new cases and new deaths. As the pandemic completes, the angle transitions to 360 degrees or near midnight. After flipping to 360 degrees, the number of new cases and new deaths has decreased and will tend to zero or a few if the pandemic ends without rebound.

7. Multiperiodic and Aperiodic Evolution

The phase space plots for Brazil, USA, and the World as a whole are shown in Figure 13. Clearly, these are currently aperiodic cases where no loop has been achieved; in the USA there have been so far the beginnings of two loops so that this case may more properly be called multiperiodic. Although parts of the USA (states and cities) as well as parts of the World (countries and cities) are somewhat controlled and have completed one cycle in phase space, as a whole a controlled cycle has not yet been achieved everywhere. Figure 14 focuses on Brazil, India, and the USA and again the two loops in the USA evolution are seen. Figure 15 explicitly shows the USA new cases evolution through late September 2020. Figure 16 compares the power spectra and Figure 17 gives the path length evolution in both the data and our standard lognormal model.

The aperiodic cases may be compared and contrasted with periodic evolution such as in Figures 1-4 for China, New Jersey, and Italy or in Figure 19 for New York City, New Jersey, and New York; similar results are found for most other regions such as Germany, France, and Italy [2].

Figure 20 gives the spectrograms for Pennsylvania, USA, and the World new deaths data. This plots the magnitude of discrete Fourier transforms of the partitions of the new deaths data [4].

This type of visualization may compliment the usual power spectra charts (e.g. Figures 10 and 16).

8. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have examined a variety of mathematical approaches to modeling the coronavirus pandemic in real time as it happens. Both the time stepped simulation and probability density function approaches reproduce the data fairly well (over .99 correlations) and allow decision makers to plan in accordance with the progress of the pandemic [11] from inception to end. A novel phase space visualization technique of plotting the number of new deaths versus the number of new cases [2] allows analysts or officials to easily see where the pandemic is in its evolution from case one to maximum and finally fading away (or rebounding). Our approach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

The author declares no competing interests, financial or otherwise. I am grateful for the past support of the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation and for participation over the summer in a VTC with members of the ITP, FIAS, University of Frankfurt focusing on the pandemic in Hungary.

References

1. Molitoris, J. and Stoecker, H. (1985), "Can We Extract the Nuclear Equation of State?", *Phase Space Approach to Nuclear Dynamics*, Singapore: World Scientific (1985) 134-152; see also Danielowicz, P. and Odyniec, G., *Phys. Lett.* 157B (1985) 146; see also Molitoris, J. (2020), "Modeling the Coronavirus Outbreak," <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/gjm6p>.
2. Molitoris, J. (2020), "Modeling the Coronavirus Outbreak," *J. Coll. Sci. Teach.* Nov. 50 (2) 36 and Molitoris, J. (1992), "Elementary and Advanced Computer Projects," *J. Coll. Sci. Teach.*, Sept. 44; see also Molitoris, J. (ed.) (2016, 2017), *Proceedings of the Capstone Project Program*, NJ: Docspicks and Molitoris, J. (2020), "Modeling the Coronavirus Outbreak," *SocArXiv* May <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/gjm6p>.
3. Kermack, W. and McKendrick, A., *Proc. of the Royal Society*, Vol. 115A (1927) 700-721.
4. Wolfram, S. (1998-2020), *The Mathematica Book*, IL: Wolfram Research.
5. World Health Organization:
<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports>
6. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention:
<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/cases-in-us.html>
7. NJ Department of Health:
https://www.nj.gov/health/cd/topics/covid2019_dashboard.shtml and
<https://www.nj.com/coronavirus/2020/03/see-the-spread-of-nj-coronavirus-in-charts-map-saturday-march-21-2020.html>
8. NYC Health:
<https://www1.nyc.gov/assets/doh/downloads/pdf/imm/covid-19-daily-data-summary.pdf>

See also New York, California , and other state Departments of Health online as well as country pages such as <https://www.gov.uk/coronavirus>.

9. Olkin, I., Gleser, L., Derman, C. (1980), *Probability Models and Applications*, NY: Macmillan; see also: Bluman, A. (2012), *Elementary Statistics*, NY: McGraw-Hill

10. Kadanoff, L.P. (1983), "Roads to Chaos," *Physics Today*, December, p. 46.

11. See papers at <https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/eid/spotlight/coronavirus> such as Mizumoto, K. and Chowell, G., *Emerg. Inf. Diseases*, Vol. 26 No. 6 (June 2020) eid26.06.200333.

Figure 1a. Two simulation methods (equations 1 to 4 and 9 to 12, respectively) are compared to China pandemic data to illustrate the novel phase space pandemic visualization technique.

Figure 1b. The several simulation models (equations 9 to 12) are compared to NJ pandemic data in a polar radar type plot.

Figure 2a. France phase space plots for data and simulation.

Figure 2b. Italy plot of time dependence of observables (cumulative cases, deaths) and other variables.

Figure 3. The model is applied to Pennsylvania where there are two bumps and compared to the data. The number of new confirmed new cases is shown vs. the time.

New Cases

— Data
— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Day

Figure 4. Pennsylvania phase space plots for data and simulation.

Figure 5. Pennsylvania plot of time dependence of observables (cumulative cases, deaths) and other variables.

Figure 6. Path length evolution in Pennsylvania for data and model.

Figure 7. Path length evolution in Michigan for data and model.

Figure 8. Path length evolution in Mexico for data and model.

- Data Unsmoothed
- Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)
- Data Smoothed
- Model Smoothed

Figure 9. Path length evolution in New York State for data and model.

Figure 10. A power spectrum is shown for Arizona model and data.

Figure 11. Path length after loop completion in over 20 regions (cities, states, countries) for data and model.

Figure 12. Flow angle vs. mortality in over 20 regions for data and model.

Death Flow Angle (deg)

● Data

— Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics

Figure 13. The phase space plots for Brazil, USA, and the World as a whole.

New Deaths

— Brazil
— USA
— World

Figure 14 focuses on Brazil, India, and the USA and again the two loops in the USA evolution are seen.

New Deaths

3000

2500

2000

1500

1000

500

0

0 20000 40000 60000 80000

New Cases

- Brazil
- India
- USA

Figure 15 explicitly shows the USA new cases evolution through late September 2020.

New Cases

— Data

— Model (Lognormal+Noise+Harmonics)

Figure 16 compares the power spectra for USA in model and data.

Figure 17 gives the USA path length evolution in both the data and our standard lognormal model.

Figure 18. USA plot of time dependence of observables (cumulative cases, deaths) and other variables.

Figure 19 shows data for New York City, New Jersey, and New York state.

New Deaths

- New Jersey
- New York City
- New York State

Figure 20abc. Spectrogram for Pennsylvania, USA, and the World new deaths data.

